

A tracer study of SBCS BA graduates from 2011 to 2016 in their respective professions: An evaluation of BA faculty contributions to their successes and achievements

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Abstract

The researcher made this tracer study to evaluate and emphasize the importance and valuable contributions of the BA faculty in shaping, molding, and guiding the BA students in their prospective careers and preparing them to undertake responsibilities in their respective workplaces according to their chosen profession. Graduating from college is not an assurance that students will eventually become successful in his or her chosen field. Suffice it to say that the learnings the students have gained during their years of stay in the institution may not be enough to compensate for what lies ahead in the workplaces they may find themselves in the future. The school, through its Alumni Association, should make every effort to keep tabs with their graduates and find out their places of work, how they are presently faring out, see how well they are performing, and dwell on their successes and achievements. This is simply the reason why schools have an Alumni Office, and its people should be charged with regularly monitoring the whereabouts of the school's graduates. But all this may have no bearing at all to our graduates if we will not consider the contributions of the BA faculty who served as the "wind beneath the wings" of their students and taught and inspired them to be who they are today.

Keywords: *Tracer study; Graduate survey; Contributions; Successes; Achievements.*

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Introduction

Since its humble beginnings from November 28, 2003, when it was founded by Dr. Gregorio Andaman Sr. and his charming wife Dominga, St. Dominic College of Asia has been churning out graduates from their respective specializations year in and out. From the Class of 2011 up to that of 2016, how many students have already graduated from their respective professions? Hundreds, if not thousands, and all these graduates attended in graduation rites that were held at the Philippine International Convention Center (PICC) in Pasay City, Philippines.

In the 2016 graduation ceremonies alone, around 334 students from SDCA graduated from their respective course programs in the said venue. There were 16 students who finished their Bachelor of Arts in Communication (BACOMM); three (3) who majored in a General Content course under Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEED); two (2) majors in Biological Science and two (2) in English both under Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED); 22 with a Bachelor's Degree in Psychology under the School of Arts, Sciences, and Education (SASE); 16 majors in Radiologic Technology; 25 in Nursing; 18 in Pharmacy; 10 in Physical Therapy; seven (7) in Radiologic Technology all under the School of Health Science Professions (SHSP); 33 majors in Hospitality Management; 20 majors in Tourism Management; three (3) associates in Hospitality Management; and 12 graduates under Commercial Cookery III all under

the School of International Hospitality and Tourism Management (SIHTM); and two (2) diplomats in Business under the Technical Education and Skills Development Authority (TESDA) course.

From Batch 2016, there were 28 who earned degrees in Multimedia Arts; 14 graduated in Accounting; one (1) in Accounting Technology; four (4) in Computer Science; and 28 in Information Technology. This leaves us with the Business Administration (BA) Program with four (4) who finished Entrepreneurship; 11 earned degrees in Financial Management; five (5) majors in Human Resource Development Management; five (5) in Operations Management; and 35 majors in Marketing Management. All these graduates received their diplomas at the PICC with around 20 others who finished in the Summer and October of 2015. In the 2019 Graduation Rites, the ceremonies were held for the very first time at the newly built auditorium of SDCA, perhaps to have a change of scenery and venue.

Other schools, well-known or otherwise, may have graduated a far larger number of students than SDCA. But the fact remains, that yearly, schools produce voluminous numbers of graduates with the hope that their aspiring alumni members would really be able to practice their chosen professions even from the very moment they stepped into college. Schools, like SDCA, have a far greater advantage when their Alumni Office keeps track of their graduates because this serves as a qualifying measure and determinant if their professors have truly contributed to their successes and achievements through the learnings that were imparted to them during their formative years in school.

For the BA Program, under the School of Business and Computer Studies, more particularly, how many of their graduates have been able to find places of work? There may have been quite a number of graduates who were able to land jobs in private companies; some may have even gone to work in government agencies, and perhaps there were those who opted to start a business of their own.

Yet, in whatever endeavor our BA graduates have ended up in, they would surely have put into practice all the theories and practical aspects that they had learned from their professors and mentors within the four walls of their classroom. There may be those who became successful in their respective fields and made achievements of their own, and perhaps there were those who are still treading their own roads to success and finding out what they could still be able to achieve the most.

In all of this, what roles did their respective BA faculty play in their student life? What valuable lessons and modes of inspiration did they impart to their students? Learning would not be of any good use if there were no faculty to instill that learning into the minds and hearts of their students. Thus, a great part of this study will dwell on what the contributions the BA faculty have made to ensure that our students would indeed become successful in their respective endeavors and gain their own fair share of achievements.

Review of Related Studies and Literature

There have been quite a number of tracer studies that have already been made previously to this one and by other professors as well. One of the tracer studies was made by George G. Tumamak Jr., a former Program Chair of Business Administration under SBCS, about graduates of Business Administration from 2007-2011. Tumamak's (2012) study dwelt on the importance of education to national development, mapping out student graduates to become a definite measure of a school's success and commitment to provide excellent education, politicians, and policy makers recognizing and politicizing about the centrality of good education and higher education to national development, stressing and emphasizing more on establishing more universities, colleges, and other educational institutions, creating of multi-campus arrangements through the expansion of higher education institutions and providing adequate infrastructural materials, more qualified instructors or professors, and policies on licensure examinations and many other things.

Another tracer study was done by Licauco (2015) about the Business Administration graduates of the School of Business and Computer Studies from the years 2011 to 2014. The purpose of the study was to lend some significance to the importance of a tracer study to certain schools. It also dealt with how higher education adequately respond to the manpower needs of industries both here in our country, abroad, and more specifically within the territories of our ASEAN counterparts; determine what educational conditions are available in the respondents' institution; find out how they were able to be gainfully employed and what motivated them to take up such employment; establish whether or not their work assignments were specifically related to their chosen field; establish the usefulness and contribution of both the theoretical and practical aspects of their education to their job performance; and determine their perceptions and attitudes towards their occupational characteristics, career expectations, actualizations, and changes.

Other tracer study was conducted by Virata (2014) about the graduates of Information Technology. But this tracer study shall dwell not only on the graduates, but also on the contributions of the BA faculty to the successes and achievements of their students with regards to their chosen fields (Abergos et al., 2008). A tracer study is very important and the school's future and continuing success is extremely reliant on this. A tracer study is a very helpful tool in trying to see how the students from an educational institution turn out to be the people that they strive to be with the special help and inspiration that comes from their respective professors (Albina & Sumagaysay, 2020; Cuadra et al., 2019).

The knowledge and learnings that their professors impart to them become part and parcel of their successes and achievements that they will be able to attain in their future jobs. There is no doubt that our BA graduates are capable of finding suitable jobs as much as their counterparts from other well-known schools can. Competition may be stiff, but our graduates ably stand up to such competition and are able to fill in the needs of industries where they can best put to use their profession or specialization (Arguson, 2015; Bueno, 2017).

Research Paradigm

Through this study, the School of Business and Computer Studies of SDCA will be benefitted as it will be able to find other ways and means in which to improve the performance of its BA faculty through more enhanced faculty development programs, and through more high technology means of imparting knowledge and skills to their students especially during this pandemic period. Had there not been a pandemic such as this, one way in which the BA faculty could have been able to improve their expertise as qualified professors and mentors was through a Faculty Exchange Program with other Asian countries should this have pushed through. But there is still hope and light at the end of the tunnel that this program may eventually materialize once things get back to the way they used to be, and our lives go back to normalcy.

The paradigm will simply illustrate how our graduates from 2011 to 2016 gave their answers to the researcher's survey questions that were fielded to them. That as soon as they graduated, were the graduates able to land jobs for a private company, government agency, or did some of them opt to start a business of their own? Did the graduates succeed in their chosen field and what achievements did they accomplish? What were their thoughts on the contributions made by their professors and were such contributions instrumental or attributable to their successes and achievements? What were the valuable lessons that their professors imparted to them? Did some or most of their professors inspire them to become the persons they are now? What values did their professors instill to them? What kind of guidance and teachings did their professors give to them so that they could make the right choices in their life and also with regard to their respective profession? What other contributions did their professors make to prepare them for whatever challenges they would face in their respective workplaces?

Statement of the Problem

The purpose or objective of the researcher's study is to be able to look into, evaluate, and emphasize the importance and valuable contributions made by the BA faculty and how they shaped, molded and guided their BA students in their prospective careers and prepared them to undertake serious responsibilities in their respective workplaces in accordance to their chosen fields. Did such BA faculty contributions attest to the successes and achievements of their BA student graduates?

Methodology

A descriptive type of research was used to gather data and suffice for the answers given by the graduates as to the questionnaire that was given to them. The researcher had targeted to have around twelve graduate respondents, from each year graduated from 2011 to 2016. This is a very simple tracer study, but the researcher had some difficulty in getting in touch with many of the graduates because of the pandemic, and most of them who were contacted failed to reply to the researcher, and so he had to do with whoever able to respond. Out of the twelve who were targeted, only nine were truly able to take the time to answer the researcher's questionnaire.

The questionnaire was very simple and easy to understand, and the respondents gave their answers clearly and directly. There were four male and five female graduates who willingly responded. All nine graduates responded that they all started working for a private company as soon as they graduated. But there was one who opted to shift to a government agency after having worked for a private company for some time, and one chose to start a business of her own.

Results and Discussion

To the question as to whether they had succeeded in their chosen field, all nine answered yes, but one worked as an accounting staff and later on became a Marketing Associate even if she graduated as an HRDM (Human Resource and Development Management) major. As to achievements garnered, three received awards and recognitions for their job performance; one became an "Employee of the Month;" and the other six respondents talked about their personal achievements like gaining self-confidence, individual growth, dedication to their work, working as front liner during this pandemic, and gaining more experience, learnings, skills, and friends.

All nine respondents answered with a resounding "yes" that the contributions made by their professors indeed become instrumental and were attributable to their successes and achievements. Through the many learnings and teachings of their professors, these allowed them to experience many things as a preparation for what they would face in the workplace. Respondents relied on the pieces of advice and life lessons imparted to them by their professors as these molded them, and with their professor's continuous guidance, they gained more knowledge to build on their skills to become eventually successful.

To the question, "What valuable lessons did their professors impart to them?" All nine respondents answered yes; there were valuable lessons that their professors imparted to them such as patience, respect, determination, to never give up, to be hardworking and be a team player, to be humble, to have dedication, to be competent, to know how to make wise and smart decisions, and be able to incorporate whatever they have learned in school to whatever work it is that they will find in their workplaces.

As to the values that were instilled in them the most by their professors, the respondents answered positively "yes" to values such as resiliency, self-confidence, having passion for what they do, being positive in their approach to life's lessons, being honest and kind, being optimistic and morally upright,

being responsible persons, obtain leadership skills, being effective and efficient and aiming to be globally competitive.

Did their professors guide and teach them well to be able to make the right choices in their life and with regards to their chosen field? To this question, all nine respondents answered yes, and said that their professors guided them well, taught them how to deal right with people when making transactions, how to handle conflicts at work, to understand the pros and cons of their chosen profession, when and where to apply life's lessons and how to aim for self-growth.

To the question, "What other contributions did your professors give to prepare you for whatever challenges you might face in your workplace?" The nine respondents almost gave the same answers as having self-confidence and self-esteem, being able to do better at work, being capable of handling and managing all adversities and setbacks, and that their professors contributed much to building and developing their character, advised them to always be thankful for all their experiences that they gained, to be consistent and to always do their best, and to always set a good example to others.

Finally, how did their professors inspire them to become the persons they now are? To this question, nine respondents all answered positively "yes," and that the inspirations they got were through the exemplary actions and dealings of their professors. They acted not only as their second parents in school, but they also became their role models. Their professors encouraged them to be the best versions of themselves, to strive hard to succeed, and motivated them to make the best out of everything that they do.

It can be gleaned from the researcher's methodology that our graduate-respondents were not to be outdone by other graduates of other schools or even by graduates from exclusive schools as well. From this very simple tracer study, it can be seen that our graduates gave a lot of value and emphasis to the contributions that were given by their professors and that such became very instrumental and even attributable to their successes and achievements in their respective professions.

BA students depend a lot on what professors can impart to them, not only in terms of what they learn or is taught to them through their formal subjects, but also in terms of life-giving values and lessons from which the students can gain a lot and make use of in their future endeavors. Indeed, the BA faculty take pains in doing everything they can to make their students turn out for the better. This is why much of their research has been focused not so much on the students themselves, but more so on the BA faculty and to properly evaluate and give due emphasis to the contributions they have given so that their students could really become successful in their respective specializations and make achievements of their own which would always form part of their ultimate goal.

Conclusions and Recommendations

It was never expected that a pandemic of such great proportion such as this COVID-19 would hit the country and almost many other parts of the world with grave seriousness that it caught everyone flat-footed. Before the pandemic, schools operated at a normal pace and teaching was dispensed with, with not much difficulty. Learning became much more interesting because there was a lot of interaction between the students and their professors because of face-to-face interactions. Faculty members could relay their lessons to the students in a more formal, if not cordial way so that they could give the needed guidance and learnings to their students and make them more interesting and interactive, coupled with their own very personal touch. Because of these personal encounters that the students had then, all the more were they encouraged and inspired to ingrain into their hearts and minds all the teachings, learnings, values, valuable lessons, and pieces of advice that their professors imparted to them.

But now, a year after the pandemic struck, the face of education completely and drastically changed, and everything became so very impersonal. Everything is virtually taught online using different forms of medium such as Google Classroom and Blackboard Learn. Neither the students nor the faculty are

to be blamed for this. For this is the modern era of social media, of high technology, such technology has the pandemic to be thankful for.

In spite of this, our students have not been wanting on what they need to learn and neither have the faculty. If then, but more so now, and as a recommendation by the researcher, the faculty need also to keep themselves updated on the latest technologies so as not to be left behind and wanting. They will need to learn this new technology more specially now than ever, because of this pandemic, almost everything is now resorted to online. Even the ordering of food, transportation, and other things are all being done online, not only because it is more convenient, but also because it is so very hard to go out nowadays with the enhanced community quarantines (ECQs), modified enhanced community quarantines (MECQs), and general community quarantines (GCQs) being declared every now and then.

Because we now live in the age of the pandemic, which has already exacted a severe toll not only in the lives of many people, but also in their means of livelihood, how can the BA faculty contribute more now to the successes and achievements of their BA students who are about to graduate? Faculty members should keep themselves updated on the latest trends in dispensing their lessons and teachings to their students and level themselves up by attending online webinars, taking advantage of the Faculty Development Programs that are always being conducted by SDCA at the start of every semester. They should also keep themselves updated on various faculty trainings being offered online to further improve their teaching know-hows. Maybe, once this pandemic is over and done with, perhaps under the new normal way of life, if ever it does happen, they could participate in Faculty Exchange Programs both local and abroad to further develop themselves and their expertise in teaching. Of course, they could still give valuable life lessons, advice, and counseling even if they are online, and add their own personal touch as they see fit.

There are so many things that the BA faculty can do, and so many ways that can be resorted to, they just need to always be aware and be in touch with everything that is happening around them. On the other hand, students must always be open to whatever their professors teach them online and be ready, willing and be able to accept and learn as this will always be a gauge that they could rely on if they are really bent on becoming successful in their chosen careers and desiring to achieve much more in their future life.

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